

FAIR Policy:

ARDC or ARDC Co-invested Materials

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Type	Policy
Owner	Director of Outreach
Approved By	CEO
Category	Projects
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Audience	External
Content Enquiries	contact@ardc.edu.au
Related Documents	FAIR Guideline for ARDC Co-Investment Project Data Outputs Guideline for Partners: Exceptions on openness of Partnership Materials

<p>Definitions</p>	<p>ARDC - Australian Research Data Commons Limited.</p> <p>Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) means all copyright, patents, registered and unregistered trademarks (including service marks), registered designs, and other rights resulting from intellectual activity (other than moral rights under the Copyright Act 1968 (Cth)).</p> <p>Material includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reports Publications Videos Images Data Software Workflows Algorithms
<p>Purpose</p>	<p>ARDC recognises that Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable inputs and outputs of research drive research innovation, impact, and quality.</p> <p>Researchers and the broader community stand to benefit from the knowledge produced by publicly-funded activities. The ARDC is committed to maximising this benefit by ensuring that the outputs of the ARDC and ARDC co-invested project activities are disseminated as widely as possible and in a manner which enables maximum reuse by humans and machines.</p>
<p>Policy Statement</p>	<p>The ARDC requires the application of the FAIR principles to ARDC’s own materials and to materials from co-invested projects unless there is a valid reason why the principles cannot be applied, and this is accepted by ARDC.</p>
<p>Background</p>	<p>Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. (2016) The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 Accessed from https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18</p>

Application of the policy

<p>Approach to implementing the FAIR Principles</p>	<p>The ARDC provides guidelines and workflows for staff within ARDC to provide clarity on how ARDC outputs can be made FAIR or valid cases for exception.</p> <p>The ARDC works with partners to define what FAIR means for co-investment project outputs and defines steps to implement FAIR in the project. The specific approach to FAIR data in co-investment projects is described in the related guideline.</p> <p>The ARDC expects project outputs to be made FAIR and where possible openly available. There are valid reasons why outputs cannot be made openly available. These are described in the related guideline.</p>
<p>Relation to Intellectual Property of partners' materials</p>	<p>Partners in ARDC activities will often own IPR in materials produced or used in ARDC projects.</p> <p>Specific arrangements related to IPR in Materials are prescribed in ARDC contracts with partners.</p>